

Original article

Spectrum of gynaecological and obstetric histopathological diagnoses in a tertiary centre in north-eastern Nigeria: a three-year retrospective study

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Abstract

Background: Understanding the histopathological patterns of gynaecological diseases is essential for guiding clinical decisions, resource distribution, and public health strategies, especially in resource-limited settings. This study aimed to evaluate the spectrum of obstetric and gynaecological diagnoses in north-eastern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A retrospective review was performed on all gynaecological and obstetric specimens received by the Department of Histopathology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State, over three years (January 2022 - December 2024). Data on patient age, tissue type, and histopathological diagnosis were collected and analysed. Diagnoses were grouped as benign, malignant, or pre-malignant. **Results:** The total number of cases was 285; 27 in 2022, 117 in 2023 and 114 in 2024. The average age was 36.4 ± 14.3 years. Benign conditions were predominant, representing 82.8% (n = 236) of cases, the commonest being pregnancy-related conditions (products of conception and its variants, 29.8%, n = 85), while malignancies constituted 12.3% (n = 35). Women aged 20-29 mainly had pregnancy-related issues (45.9%), while those aged 30-49 primarily had leiomyomas. The rate of malignancies increased with age, from 4.1% in women aged 20-29 to 58.8% in women aged ≥ 60 years. The most frequent cancers were ovarian carcinoma (22.9%), endometrial carcinoma (17.1%), and squamous cell carcinoma of the cervix (17.1%). **Conclusion:** This study highlights the high burden of pregnancy-related conditions and benign tumours like leiomyomas, with a notable presence of gynaecological cancers, especially among older women, underscoring the need for better diagnosis, screening, and treatment infrastructure.

Keywords: Gynaecological diseases, Histopathological pattern, Obstetric diseases

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Introduction

Gynaecological and obstetric histopathology provides useful data on benign, premalignant, and malignant lesions of the female genital tract, for case management and health-system planning.^{1,2} Cervical, ovarian, and endometrial carcinomas predominate the female genital tract malignancies in Nigeria.^{3,4} In northeastern Nigeria, cervical carcinoma accounted for about two-thirds (66.6%) of gynaecologic cancers over four years, followed by uterine corpus and ovarian cancers.³

The workload of histopathological specimens comes mainly from non-malignant gynaecologic and obstetric specimens and Nigerian endometrial-biopsy data available show that non-neoplastic lesions dominate, with products of conception as the most frequent in reproductive age, reflecting a high burden of early pregnancy loss and incomplete miscarriages.⁵⁻⁷ while malignancy is largely confined to peri- and postmenopausal women.^{8,9} Less common entities like Gestational trophoblastic disease (GTD) contribute significantly to maternal morbidity.¹

This three-year retrospective review in a tertiary centre in northeastern Nigeria is therefore aimed at characterising the spectrum and relative frequencies of benign, premalignant, and malignant lesions of the cervix, uterus, adnexa, vulva, vagina, and pregnancy-related tissue.

This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the observed histopathologic findings in obstetric and gynaecological specimens within a tertiary institution in North-Eastern Nigeria, addressing the paucity of detailed regional data. Such an investigation is crucial for understanding the local prevalence of various gynaecological and obstetric diseases, thereby informing clinical management protocols and public health interventions.³

Materials and Methods

This was a 3-year retrospective descriptive study conducted at the Department of Histopathology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare. Histopathological reports of obstetric and gynaecological specimens received from January 2022 to December 2024 were reviewed. Demographic and clinical data were retrieved from departmental archives. Specimens included biopsies, curettings, and resection samples. Data were analysed to determine frequencies, age distribution, and proportions of benign versus malignant lesions using SPSS version 26.

Results

The total number of cases was 285; 27 in 2022, 117 in 2023 and 141 in 2024. The average age was 36.4 ± 14.3 years. This is illustrated in Table 1. The average age was 36.4 ± 14.3 years. Benign diseases accounted for 87.4% (n=249) of all diagnoses. Smooth muscle diseases and reproductive

disorders dominate the clinical picture within this benign category: Product of conception (POC) and gestational trophoblastic diseases accounted for 29.8% (n=85) of all cases, this is followed by Uterine leiomyomas, which accounted for 16.5% (n=47) of all cases. See Table 2.

Table 1: showing cases distribution by year

Year	Number of cases	Benign (%)	Malignant (%)
2022	27	23 (85.2)	4 (14.8)
2023	117	101(86.3)	16 (13.7)
2024	141	97 (85.1)	17 (14.9)
Total	285	249 (87.4)	36 (12.6)

Table 2: Age-specific pathology pattern of obstetrics and gynaecology cases in Azare

Age group	Dominant pathology (%)	Malignancy rate	Key findings
0-9	-	-	-
10-19	Pregnancy related (66.9)	0	Benign conditions
20-29	Pregnancy related (45.9)	4.1	Reproductive
30-39	Leiomyoma (27.2)	12.3	Mixed pathology
40-49	Leiomyoma (32.6)	19.6	Raising malignancy
50-59	UV prolapse (28.0)	28.0	High malignancy rate
60-69	Carcinoma (58.8)	58.8	Predominantly malignant

Key: UV= Utero-vaginal

Women in their third decade of life were predominantly affected by pregnancy-related conditions (45.9%). In contrast, the 30-49 age group showed a significant shift toward neoplastic diseases, with leiomyomas being the leading diagnosis. The malignancy rate rose sharply from 4.1% in the 20-29 age group to 58.8% in women aged 60 and above. This is illustrated in figure 1.

Ovarian carcinoma was the most frequent malignancy encountered, accounting for 22.9%. This was followed by cervical squamous cell carcinoma and endometrial carcinoma (17.1% each) (Figure 2).

Figure 1: showing a dominant pathology vs malignancy rate by age group (years)

Figure 2: Showing the distribution of cases by tissue type

Table 3. Table Showing Diagnostic Performance of Leukocyte Esterase Against Urine Culture

Leukocyte Esterase	Culture Positive	Culture Negative	Total
LE Positive	25	12	37
LE Negative	9	99	108
Total	34	111	145

Discussion

The study highlights the significant burden of gynaecological and obstetric conditions in the region, emphasising the predominance of benign conditions such as products of conception (POC) and leiomyomas. It also highlights the high prevalence of malignant conditions such as ovarian and cervical cancers. This is consistent with previous studies demonstrating high prevalence of these diseases, likely due high rate of reproduction in our community.¹⁰⁻¹²

The high frequency of POC specimens suggests ongoing issues related to pregnancy loss, reflecting gaps in family planning and post-abortion care services in the region. This is consistent with findings from previous studies suggesting POC-related complications as common in regions with high fertility rates, often exceeding 5-8 children per woman.⁶ The prevalence of leiomyomas in Nigerian women remains high, with some studies indicating prevalence rates up to 80% among women over 30,

contributing to anaemia, pelvic pain, and infertility – thus increasing the surgical burden.^{11,13} The study's observed age-pathology correlation aligns with global and African data, which suggests younger women predominantly experience pregnancy-related issues; mid-life women face benign tumours like leiomyomas; while older women develop malignant diseases such as ovarian and uterine cancers.^{14,15} The marked increase – up to 60% – in malignancy rates among post-menopausal women highlights a systemic failure in early detection and prevention, as late-stage disease cases often result in poor outcomes.^{14,15}

Ovarian cancer was found to be the commonest malignancy in the study. This is however different from findings in other studies which showed cervical cancer as the most prevalent malignancy.^{16,17,18} This may be due to pap screening and HPV vaccination for cervical cancer or due to the relatively short study duration of this study. On the other hand, there is no recognised screening

method effective for public health prevention of ovarian cancer.

The findings affirm that Nigeria's gynaecological health challenges are rooted in systemic inadequacies encompassing family planning, reproductive health services, and cancer prevention strategies. The reliance on reactive care rather than proactive, preventive approaches leads to high rates of late-stage malignancies and morbidity.^{19,20,21} This study was a three-year audit of all the cases submitted to the histopathology department. Its strengths include the use of confirmed histopathological diagnoses, which help reduce misclassification of cases. The study also provides valuable regional data where published histopathological audits are limited and age-based analysis of cases was done. Limitations of the study include its retrospective single-centre design as well as a relatively small sample size.

Conclusion

This study revealed a rising trend in gynaecological pathology diagnoses, from 27 cases in 2022 to 141 in 2024, affecting mostly young and middle-aged women. Benign conditions predominate, led by products of conception, followed by gestational trophoblastic diseases and uterine leiomyomas. Age-specific patterns show pregnancy-related conditions peaking at 3rd decade of life. Neoplastic diseases, particularly leiomyomas, predominated in the 4th decade and malignancy rates increased dramatically with age. The findings also reflect the reproductive health burden in the population and highlight the significant influence of age on disease patterns, particularly the risk of malignancy in older women.

Based on the findings from the study, we recommend a multiple strategy to reshape gynaecological care in North-eastern Nigeria and similar settings. These include the implementation of age-stratified clinical services. Also, enhanced adolescent and youth-friendly clinics: focused on robust family planning and safe motherhood services to address the high burden of pregnancy-related conditions.

We also recommend Surgery Units to efficiently manage the high volume of symptomatic leiomyomas, reducing the burden on major surgical theatres in addition to dedicated Gynaecologic Oncology and Menopause Clinics to provide specialized care for the high-risk post-menopausal population, focusing on early diagnosis and treatment of cancers.

Finally, there is need to establish a hospital-based cancer registry to enable robust tracking of

outcomes and quality of care. Further research is recommended to include clinical presentations of the patients and also to evaluate prognostic markers of the malignant conditions.

Investing in these targeted, evidence-driven recommendations will not only alleviate the current burden of disease but also fundamentally transform the landscape of women's health in our region, saving lives and resources in the long term.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualisation – R.Y, U.S.E, J.M, G.A.S, D.A.K.

Methodology (design) – R.Y, J.M, G.A.S, U.S.E, D.A.K, A.A.J.

Data analysis – R.Y, P.O.O, T.H.O, U.S.E, S.E.A.

Initial write-up – R.Y, U.S.E, E.O.A, T.H.O, P.O.O.

Final write-up – R.Y, A.A.J, J.M, T.H.O, U.S.E, S.E.A, E.O.A, K.D.A.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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